

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for **African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.**

D3.6 Trans-Continental Partnership Building Flagship Programme

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Glossary and Abbreviations

DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
Q&A	Questions and Answers
IoT	Internet of Things
AI	Artificial Intelligence
IP	Intellectual Property
Tech	Technology
Intro	Introduction
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic, and Timely
VUCA	Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity

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Executive Summary

AfriConEU is developing, testing, and validating the “AfriConEU Networking Academy,” an innovative mechanism for connecting African and European DIHs. The Academy will comprise two flagships, one dedicated to Capacity Building and another to Trans-Continental Partnership development. This deliverable addresses the latter. The Trans-Continental Partnership Building Flagship Programme aims to offer concrete opportunities for networking and exchange between African and European DIHs and their communities of practitioners and stimulate the creation of collaborative projects and ventures development. It will be composed of four sub-programmes/ themes, namely:

1. Towards a common digital market and a connected start-up ecosystem;
2. Digitalisation, jobs for the 21st century and employment opportunities;
3. Business and investment opportunities in the African market;
4. Scouting digital entrepreneurs and start-ups in the African market.

To deliver this programme, partners will organise: i) one International Brokerage event; ii) four Design Thinking Bootcamps among African and European DIHs; iii) one Capitalization event; iv) and targeted interventions through the online knowledge-sharing community of the project.

The Deliverable 3.6 is a document presenting the objectives and the sub-programmes included together with the expected outcomes and Key Performance Indicators (KPI). It also includes the results from the international participative design workshop organized by AfriConEU to discuss the programme and presents how they were incorporated into it.

1. Introduction

AfriConEU aims at developing the **first Networking Academy** between African and European DIHs with the aim to: (i) facilitate knowledge and experience sharing, (ii) drive the development of mutually beneficial partnerships and (iii) support the creation of collective projects for boosting digital economy, empowering youth and women and fostering innovation and growth. The AfriConEU Networking Academy will be composed of two Flagships Programmes: (i) the Capacity Building Flagship Programme; (ii) and the Trans-Continental Partnerships Building Flagship Programme. The first was designed and addressed in Deliverables *D3.1 - Capacity Building Flagship Programme*, *D3.2 - Structure and training material for local workshops*, *D3.3 - Webinars Content and Design*, *D3.4 - Inventory of capacity building resources and ready to use training material* and *D3.5 - Online Masterclasses*. The present document aims to address the second flagship, presenting its structure, the contents, tools to deliver the contents and KPI to monitor and assess the success of the programme.

The programme is designed based on the results from:

- (i) an international participative design workshop organised by AfriConEU to discuss with the wider community the most appropriate objectives, thematic areas, methods and tools for this Flagship programme. The details and results of this workshop can be consulted in [Annex 1](#).
- (ii) an analysis conducted by the AfriConEU consortium targeting the identification of needs and opportunities for transcontinental collaboration and which was presented in *D2.4 - Challenges and Opportunities for Trans-Continental Collaboration* ([Annex 2](#) provide a short report produced for the international workshop and which contains the main outcomes of D2.4 and the suggested structure, methods, tools and foreseen outcomes of the “AfriConEU Networking Academy”).

It is divided into four sub-programmes/ themes and will be delivered through: i) one International Brokerage event; (ii) four Design Thinking Bootcamps; (iii) one Capitalization event; (iv) and targeted interventions through the Community of Practice of the project.

[Chapter 2](#) of this deliverable presents a general overview of this Flagship Programme, providing details on its objectives, expected outcomes, structure and sub-programmes. And [Chapter 3](#) gives details on the activities that will be implemented, providing preliminary structures and agendas of the activities.

2. Overall presentation of the Programme

2.1. Objectives (short-term)

- Engage African and European DIHs, entrepreneurs, start-ups, enterprises, investors, African Diaspora communities, Pan-African networks, policy-makers
- Provide participants practical ways to connect and collaborate
- European investors and entrepreneurs get familiar with the African market and opportunities in Africa
- 10 strategic connections to support collaboration between the European and African innovation ecosystems
- 30 ideas/ prototypes for joint projects with European partners
- Networking and matching activities are performed between participants
- Collaboration channels are presented

2.2. Expected outcomes (medium/long-term)

- African DIH gain access to European Networks of investors and collaborators
- New Africa-Europe partnerships established
- Creating, expanding and strengthening networks between the African and European innovation ecosystems
- Development of common projects for i) improving start-ups' support and digitalisation and ii) skills development (design joint-programmes)
- Resources and fund sharing

2.3. Structure

The Trans-Continental Partnerships Building Flagship Programme is divided into four sub-programmes (as detailed next). Nevertheless, it will be delivered as a single programme, encompassing all four themes.

The programme will:

- (1) begin with an **International Brokerage event**;
- (2) followed by four **bootcamps** with the same content and structure that will be delivered in the four African countries;
- (3) during the programme, **targeted interventions** will be applied to promote the exchange of knowledge and experiences, mainly due to the fact that participants are located on different continents. Participants will be invited to use the Discord platform to chat and share documents through the link: <https://discord.gg/ZWQ59sAZyd>. These interventions should include materials such as readings and case studies;

(4) at the end, a Capitalization event will be organised;

Figure 1 presents the timeline of this Flagship Programme, as well as the main Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for each planned activity.

Figure 1. AfriConEU Trans-Continental Partnership Building Flagship Programme Activities: calendar and KPI.

2.4. Sub-programmes

SUB-PROGRAMME #1: Towards a common digital market and a connected start-up ecosystem

Tentative short title: Africa-Europe connected ecosystem

This sub-programme will bring together digital ecosystem stakeholders from both continents. The goal is to facilitate new partnerships and common projects development for improving start-ups support and digitalisation.

SUB-PROGRAMME #2: Digitalisation, jobs for the 21st century and employment opportunities

Tentative short title: DigiEmploy

This sub-programme will bring together stakeholders from Africa and Europe to design common projects and solutions for 21st-century skills development and a better matching of skills supply and demand between the two continents. Taking into account the increasing youth population in Africa and considering that both continents are suffering from the absence of workforce with ICT skills, as well as from youth unemployment, a strategic partnership in this field is essential for the mutual benefit of both continents. Therefore, under this topic, we aim at stimulating the collective intelligence of stakeholders to design joint programmes and initiatives for competences development and a better matching of skills supply and demand between the two continents.

SUB-PROGRAMME #3: Business and investment opportunities in the African market

Tentative short title: Africa Businvest

This sub-programme addresses networking and matchmaking activities between DIHs, entrepreneurs, investors, African diaspora communities, representatives from Pan-African networks, policymakers from AU and EC. etc. with the aim to explore market and investment opportunities in Africa. It also aims to enable: i) African DIHs to gain access to valuable networks comprising investors and potential partners, ii) European Investors and entrepreneurs to get familiar with African markets as well as with business development opportunities in Africa; iii) African Diaspora communities to meet potential partners to invest back in their countries.

SUB-PROGRAMME #4: Scouting digital entrepreneurs and start-ups in the African market

Tentative short title: African Entrepreneurs

One of the main issues in operating a DIH is building trust and convincing users that digital services are the future of Africa. It is crucial to reach and engage a wide network of creators, entrepreneurs and start-ups. The goal of the theme is, therefore, to understand what and where digital entrepreneurs are to match them with DIHs in Europe and Africa.

3. Programme Activities

3.1. International Brokerage Event

An AfriConEU International brokerage event will launch the Trans-Continental Partnership Building Flagship Programme, bringing together DIHs, entrepreneurs, investors, African diaspora communities, representatives from Pan-African networks, policymakers, among other relevant stakeholders. The brokerage event will start with a presentation of the AfriConEU programmes and culminate in specially designed networking and matchmaking sessions.

The preliminary details of the event are presented below:

Date, venue, organisers

Date: 29-30 September 2022

Venue: Bologna, Italy and African DIH

Organisers: DPIXEL (main org.), all partners of AfriConEU

KPIs:

- +200 participants;
- +10 African DIHs representatives attending;
- +10 strategic partnerships;
- Single, multi-day event;
- European base;
- Hybrid model with remote hubs collaborating with main event;
- Mixed audience between investors, support networks, entrepreneurs, DIH teams, and African, European and diaspora communities.

Preliminary structure:

The Brokerage event is planned as a:

hybrid and multi-site event:

- The primary event will take place in Bologna Italy, and convene representatives from various stakeholder groups from both the African and European ecosystems and the diaspora community.
- In parallel, African DIH partners will host local events for their ecosystems, livestreaming the activities from Bologna, presenting local speakers and providing opportunities to engage with the central event.

2-day event:

- The first day will focus on a cycle of vertical presentations on strategic sectors for African Innovation Ecosystems, such as Agri Tech, Ed Tech, Fin Tech, ICT4D, and Med Tech, with transversal themes covering the critical areas for the AfriConEU project (i.e. the four sub-programmes of the Trans-

Continental Partnership Building Flagship Programme) – *consult design thinking bootcamps for more information on the sub-programmes presentation (Day #0)*. These will be interspersed with opportunities to network and unpack themes emerging from the talks.

- The second day is oriented toward interactive sessions. The opening part of the day will focus on framing the themes to be explored by the AfriConEU project, highlighting the transversal elements from the first day. Then, participants will be moved into collaborative activities, such as world cafes, and brainstorming activities, where they will be encouraged to find possible opportunities for collaboration and partnership. The final part of the event will transition into focused speed dating and matchmaking sessions.
- Throughout the event, participants, both onsite in Bologna and remote from the hub locations, will have the opportunity to sign up for speed networking appointments with other participants. One objective of these meetings is to help establish strategic bilateral relationships that can help develop their respective innovation ecosystems. A second objective is to frame challenges and opportunities which can be fed into the bootcamp events for further development.

3.2. Design thinking bootcamps

The connections made during the International Brokerage Event will be further supported to continue and evolve with the organisation of 4 design thinking bootcamps that will take place in each one of the targeted African countries aiming to bring together digital ecosystem stakeholders and experts from Europe and Africa and facilitate knowledge and experience sharing towards common projects development. The bootcamps will be also open to individuals not participating in the Brokerage Event.

The four bootcamps will follow the same structure. Nevertheless, the planned structure is sufficiently flexible to integrate any possible adjustment resulting from the local needs.

The preliminary details of the bootcamps are presented below:

Date, venue, organisers

Date: July 2023 (planned)

Venue: Nigeria, Ghana, Tanzania and Uganda

Organisers: Outbox, ECA, Hapa and Buni (main orgs.), all partners of AfriConEU

KPIs:

- 4 bootcamps ;
- 4 African countries (1 bootcamp/country): Nigeria, Ghana, Tanzania and Uganda;
- 3 days (+ Day 0) each bootcamp;
- Face-to-face (with possibility of hybrid format, if needed);
- +40 participants each bootcamp;
- Mixed teams: African and European DIH, Start-ups and enterprises;
- Gender balance;
- +30 ideas/prototypes co-designed for joint projects with African-EU partners (~7-8/ bootcamp);
- 5-6 facilitators.

Preliminary structure:

Each bootcamp is planned as a 3+0 day activity:

#Day 0 – the Getting Ready Day:

The first day of the bootcamp does not have a fixed date to occur. It translates an estimation of the time that bootcamp’s participants need to prepare for the bootcamp challenges. The “Getting Ready Day” express a set of keynotes and other actions addressing the 4 sub-programmes of the Trans-Continental Partnership Building Flagship Programme. These keynotes and activities will be organised as part of the Brokerage Event and/ or recorded after that event. As such, interested individuals have two main formats to access the activities composing the “Getting Ready Day”: one is through participation in the Brokerage Event, and another is by watching the recordings.

To watch the recordings no registration will be necessary. To attend the 3-day bootcamp, interested individuals will need to register by completing an online form that will ask about personal contacts and a set of questions that will support the AfriConEU team to prepare the matching to form the teams during the bootcamps (which needs? Which interests and objectives for the bootcamp? Which ideas, if any, for a potential project? Etc.).

Format of Sub-programmes Presentation to be held during, preferably, Brokerage Event		
What?	Description	Time
Presentation of the 1 st Sub-programme:		
<i>Towards a common digital market and a connected start-up ecosystem</i> (Talk with an expert)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Context - Challenges & Opportunities - Legal, cultural and language barriers - Example of concrete collaborations (sharing good practices) - Network channels - Practices to avoid: Lessons learned from Europe and Africa - Platforms to promote Africa-Europe collaboration and its features (funding opportunities, networking) 	50min
Suggestion of problems to be addressed by the 1 st sub-programme to motivate discussion by stakeholders:		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Practical ways to connect both ecosystems - Design a joint project for improving start-up’s support and digitalisation - How to engage the grassroots? 		
Presentation of the 2 nd Sub-programme:		
<i>Digitalisation, jobs for the 21st century and employment opportunities</i> (Talk with an expert)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evolving labour market - Presentation of the 21st century skills/ competences of the future - Leadership - Communication - Co-creation - Team Working & Interpersonal Effectiveness - Technological Know-how in areas like AI, deeptech, hardware 	10 min
Suggestion of problems to be addressed by the 2 nd sub-programme to motivate discussion by stakeholders:		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How to solve youth and women main challenges in the employment world? - Design an incentive model that is not merely economic for both continents to collaborate - Design a joint programme for competence development - How can the talent be attracted and retained? - How can the skills' supply and demand be matched between continents? 		
Introduction to the 3 rd Sub-programme:		
Business and investment opportunities in the African market (Talk with an expert)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overview of the African market - Business partnerships (Europe-Africa, Africa-Africa) - Funding and investment opportunities - Shared funding, Exchange programs - Real examples 	35 min
Suggestion of problems to be addressed by the 3 rd sub-programme to motivate discussion by stakeholders:		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can we prevent brain drain? - How to pitch to local investors? - How to search for business and investment opportunities? - How to access investor networks? - How can African Diaspora know opportunities to invest back in their countries? 		
Introduction to the 4 th Sub-programme:		
Scouting digital entrepreneurs and start-ups in the African market (Talk with an expert)	Defining digital entrepreneurs and their skills Challenges for African start-ups to enter the market: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Infrastructures and skills gap - Lack of enabling policies - Lack of trust, - Information gap The role of the African Diaspora in building sustainable start-ups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - investor and start-up matching activities - innovation showcases and presentations - network with African diaspora groups and individuals - open calls for funding (cascade funding) - structured investment funds to bring trust - platforms for exchanges 	25min
Suggestion of problems to be addressed by the 4 th sub-programme to motivate discussion by stakeholders:		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Where can digital entrepreneurs be found? - What are the most suitable activities for enterprises and start-ups/ entrepreneurs to collaborate? Mentoring? - How can African start-ups pilot their solutions in the European context? 		

#Day 1 – the Ideation Day (~6,5 hours):

The first day of the bootcamp will be dedicated to motivating participants to know each other and to explore potential ideas for their projects. The agenda will be, thus, focused on networking and design thinking activities.

What?	Description	Time
Welcome	Presentation of the bootcamp programme, its objectives and expected results - by AfriConEU partner	10 min

Inspirational speech	Setting the scene for the African-European partnerships in a DIH perspective <i>- by AfriConEU partner or guest involved in a successful case of Africa-Europe cooperation</i>	10min
Warm-up	- 30-seconds pitch self-presentation (name, organisation and role in the organisation) <i>- by participants</i>	25 min
Networking	Possible formats: - coffee-break with free talking style; - challenge: participants are challenged to interact with the maximum number of participants and ask them 2-3 questions to know more about their experience and what they look for during the bootcamp. The people with more interactions win a symbolic prize; <i>- with participants</i>	40 min
Mapping	Mapping of expertise and objectives of participants, based on the information collected by participants in the previous activity <i>- by facilitator, with the support of participants</i> <i>- Suggested tools: mind map, post its.</i>	60 min
Lunchtime (90 min) All participants are invited to lunch in the same place and continue interacting.		
Warm-up	Setting up teams (8-10 teams)	20 min
Teamwork	Definition of the problem and project ideas per team <i>- by participants, with support of facilitators who will guide participants in implementing ideation tools.</i> <i>- Ideation techniques' suggested tools: brainstorming, world café</i> <i>- No break will be organised. To provide coffee and snacks during the activity.</i>	150 min

Day 2 – the Consolidation Day (~6 hours):

The second day of the bootcamp shall stimulate the consolidation of the ideas generated the day before. For this reason, the agenda will be focused on implementing design thinking activities that support participants to develop more their ideas. Furthermore, participants shall start preparing the information to be shared on the third day of the bootcamp.

What?	Description	Time
Warm-up	Presentation of the second-day agenda, its objectives and expected results + Ice breaker <i>- by AfriConEU partner</i>	15 min
Teamwork	Consolidating problem and project idea <i>Suggested tools: brainstorming, world café</i> <i>- by participants, with support of facilitators who will guide participants in implementing ideation tools.</i> <i>- Ideation techniques' suggested tools: brainstorming, world café</i> <i>- No break will be organised. To provide coffee and snacks during the activity.</i>	115 min
Lunchtime (90 min) All participants are invited to lunch in the same place and continue interacting.		
Teamwork	Ideation synthesis <i>- by participants, with the support of facilitators who will guide participants in implementing tools.</i> <i>- Suggested tools: cluster, dot voting, ideation matrix</i>	60 min

Teamwork	Concept and Project definition and prototyping; preparing the next day <i>- by participants, with the support of facilitators</i> <i>- Suggested tools: idea napkin, concept canvas, business model canvas, wizard of oz, wireframes, cardboard</i>	150 min
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Day 3 – the Presentation Day (~7 hours):

The third and final day of the bootcamp will encourage participants to share their projects with the other participants and share feedback. Investors and other relevant stakeholders will be invited to this day to provide feedback to the teams.

What?	Description	Time
Warm-up	Presentation of the third-day agenda, its objectives and expected results <i>- by AfriConEU partner</i>	10 min
Pitch #1	Presentation of Teams projects ideas / prototypes: - 7 min presentation per project/ team. - 7 min feedback from other participants through an online tool (such as mentimeter, sli.do or other). The facilitator shall prepare the online tool with 2-3 questions for each of the teams of the bootcamp. The questions shall be the same (e.g. Main strengths of the project? Issues to be improved?) <i>- by participants</i>	150 min
Lunchttime (60 min) All participants are invited to lunch in the same place and continue interacting.		
Pitch #2	Pitch to real users and investors: - 7 min presentation per project/ team. - 7 min feedback from users and investors invited to the bootcamp <i>- by participants and external stakeholders</i>	150 min
Towards the future	Closing Session + Networking Closing Session, wrapping up the bootcamp and launching the last networking moment to foster collaboration and explore the feedback from users and investors. <i>- with participants and external stakeholders</i>	60 min

3.3. Capitalisation Event

At the end of the project, a final Capitalisation and Celebration Event will be organised to bring together DIHs, experts, researchers, policymakers from both continents and follow up and capitalise upon the connections created and the results achieved. The event will also reflect upon the achievements of AfriConEU, explore new opportunities for innovation generated and support policy uptake.

The preliminary details of the event are presented below:

Date, venue, organisers

Date: September 2023

Venue: to be defined

Organisers: DPIXEL (main org.), all partners of AfriConEU

KPIs:

- +400 participants
- Single, multi-day event
- Probable hybrid model
- Synthesis/completion/celebration of AfriConEU activities
- Potential to include other ICT-58 actors

Preliminary structure:

The Capitalisation event is envisaged as a closure of the Academy program. It will be a multi-day event with at least 400 participants. It may include a range of features. Some possible elements may include:

- Brief recaps of elements from the other elements of the Academy program;
- Outcomes from activities that synthesize the overall work of the project, such as the Brokerage Event and the Design Thinking Bootcamps;
- Success stories and best practices from across the AfriConEU project;
- A final recap of the work done;
- Contributions from other representatives of the ICT-58 Family (ICT-58 funded projects);
- Opportunities to create collaborative projects;
- Interactive sessions to propose and discuss projects that will carry forward the work from the AfriConEU project and the other ICT-58 Family activities.

The event may be organised in parallel with or as a component of a larger tech and innovation event, which would allow it to leverage an existing community of actors and deliver greater visibility, depending on interest and resources.

The involvement of the other ICT-58 family projects would be a useful component to consider since they could provide added context and opportunities related to the direct work of AfriConEU. In that case, the event would represent a conclusion not only of the AfriConEU networking academy but of the work of the other projects.

Given the timeline of the event, a large number of potential elements to consider and its overall reliance on the progress and outcomes of the other components of WP4, specific planning will be postponed until the second half of 2022, approximately one year in advance of the event as scheduled.

3.4. Targeted interventions through the Community of Practice of the project

In addition to the four Design Thinking Bootcamps, the International Brokerage and Capitalisation events, the AfriConEU consortium will also organise some targeted interventions through the knowledge-sharing community of the project (developed within T5.1¹) in order to fully deliver the Trans-Continental Partnership Building Flagship Programme.

Concretely, the main facilitator of the Community of Practice (INOVA+) supported by the rest of the consortium members will actively engage with all the relevant stakeholders of the project (DIHs, entrepreneurs, ecosystem builders, accelerators, mentors, start-ups, investors, corporates, members of the African Diaspora Community etc.) through a set of channels and activities together with the rest of the consortium members.

At the moment, the project's website and social media channels are the key touchpoints for the community members. Moreover, beyond this broader communication focus, AfriConEU also sets specific and more narrow channels within its website so that the project's public can interact with the consortium and inform them about what type of opportunities they are looking for. It is the case of the forms For Individuals² and For Entities³ available on the AfriConEU website whose responses enable not only to share content that interests its followers but also redirect its social media communication to specific targets, making sure the expressed requests will be fulfilled. In its turn, this information can be used to better shape the Academy programmes.

A strong collaboration with AfriConEU partners is foreseen, in particular with ECA who is leading the project's stakeholders engagement strategy (Task 4.2) and is already organising dedicated activities in the targeted African ecosystems with the aim to gather local players, inform them about the Academy's resources and activities and trigger their participation. This includes: regular community-building events like virtual discussions/ meetings between key stakeholders on the planned activities; participation in events where the AfriConEU target groups will be participating; strong online and onsite dissemination of the Programme's activities, among other activities.

¹ Details on the AfriConEU Community of Practice and its management can be consulted in Deliverable D5.7 - *The AfriConEU Community Report (Interim)*.

² <https://www.africoneu.eu/for-individuals/>

³ <https://www.africoneu.eu/for-entities/>

4. Conclusion

The Trans-continental Partnerships Building Flagship Programme of the AfriConEU Academy aims to provide tools and channels for African and European DIHs to collaborate, mainly through joint projects development, joint programmes delivery and matchmaking activities. The programme will be delivered through design thinking bootcamps, events and other initiatives.

This document presents the objectives, expected outcomes, KPIs and content of the programme, as well as the results of the International Participative Workshop and how they were integrated into the programme.

This document should be perceived as a baseline for the activities to be implemented during the project. The contents and structure were designed to be open and flexible, enabling the adaptation of the content and format by the implementing trainers. The implementation planning and details will be discussed and presented in deliverable *D4.1 – Implementation plan*.

Annex 1. International participative workshop

To develop the Trans-Continental Partnership Building Flagship, partners have initially organised an international participative workshop among consortium partners, representatives of the African and European digital innovation ecosystems, invited experts from European DIHs and Pan-African Networks.

The goal was to discuss the most appropriate objectives, thematic areas, methods and tools to be utilised for the different programmes included under this Flagship programme.

Figure 2 - Image created to promote the workshop on Facebook

The event was also promoted on the AfriConEU website: <https://www.africoneu.eu/workshop-development-of-the-trans-continental-partnerships-page/>

The workshop was organised by Porto Business School with the support of all partners. Prior to the workshop a short report containing the main outcomes of Deliverable D2.4 and the suggested structure, methods, tools and foreseen outcomes of the “AfriConEU Networking Academy” was prepared ([Annex 2](#)).

- **Suggested structure:** 3 sub-programmes delivered through Design Thinking Bootcamps among African and European DIHs, an International Brokerage event, a Capitalization event, and targeted interventions through the online knowledge-sharing community of the project (masterclasses, webinars, readings, case studies, etc.).
- **Methods:** Lecture—Showing/Telling; Video-Based Learning (VBL); Contact with experts; Discussion-Based Learning; Peer feedback; Case-based Exercises / Case studies; Challenge-Based Learning; Hands-on work
- **Tools:** design thinking bootcamps, events and training resources available on the online repository.

- **Foreseen outcomes:** leveraging DIH skills, knowledge and resources at a European and African level; connection of African DIHs with each other and with DIHs in Europe; creation of opportunities for business and growth; strengthening of the African tech hubs.
- **Expected impact:**
 - a. More than 200 stakeholders involved in the International Brokerage event;
 - b. A min of 10 African DIHs representatives to attend the Brokerage event with the aim to create a minimum of 10 connections for strategic partnerships between DIHs and European innovation ecosystem stakeholders;
 - c. African DIHs gain access to European networks of investors and collaborators;
 - d. European Investors and entrepreneurs get familiar with African markets and opportunities in Africa;
 - e. New partnerships established with African diaspora communities in Europe for supporting further African start-ups and SMEs;
 - f. More than 160 participants in design thinking bootcamps co-designing more than 30 ideas/prototypes for joint projects with EU partners.

The conclusions of the workshop were used for the design of the Partnership Building programme.

The majority of the questions were about content, namely about the thematic areas, the 21st-century skills, the common market, the investment opportunities and the entrepreneurial ecosystem. All the content discussed is embedded into the content of the programme.

There was a question about the learning journey in which participants concluded that the trainees should be active learners, meaning that the trainer is a facilitator, and that peer-to-peer learning should form a key component of capacity-building programmes. This insight is going to be integrated into the programme as there are more hours of active learning than expositive teaching.

There was a question about the characteristics that a platform to boost the partnerships should have, but AfriConEU partners decided that existing platforms should be mapped rather than developing a new one, so this part will not be addressed.

The foreseen outcomes were presented and were considered adequate to foster the skills in Africa-Europe partnerships. In the same line of thought, participants agreed with the suggested structure and referred that targeted interventions should mainly include materials such as readings and case studies.

The last questions referred to the methods to apply in the programme and the answers were the following (by descending order of votes):

1. Contact with experts
2. Case-based Exercises/ Case studies
3. Challenge-based learning
4. Lecture-showing/Telling
5. Video-Based Learning (VBL)
6. Discussion-Based Learning
7. Peer feedback
8. Hands-on work

All of these methods will be applied during the programme implementation.

Results of the international participative workshop

Thematic areas

Question 1: Do the areas previously presented seem adequate to foster skills in Africa-Europe DIH partnerships? (21st century skills development and employment opportunities; common digital market and a connected start-up ecosystem; and Business and investment opportunities in the African market)

Answers:

- Yes
- Yes. But more grassroots participation is needed.
- The list looks great but there is the need for a stronger alignment between government and the grassroots efforts on the ground.
- Yes, I think it does because there is a great knowledge sharing opportunity for mutual growth.

Question 2: Can you write down additional topics that can be added?

Answers:

- Interoperability between innovation ecosystems (mainly Africans).
- Legal and language barriers.
- High growth/impact venture creation.
- The role of the African Diaspora in building sustainable start-ups.
- Shared funding, Exchange programs.

Question 3: Which of the following represents the 21st century skills?

Answers (by descending order of votes):

1. Leadership
2. Communication

3. Co-creation
4. Team Working & Interpersonal Effectiveness
5. Technological Know-how in areas like AI, deeptech, hardware
6. Transparency and directedness in dealing with others
7. Planning Skills
8. Costumer-oriented
9. Delegating and supporting organization
10. Cross-functional perspective
11. Concern for excellence
12. Risk Taking

Question 4: How is the learning journey perceived?

Answers (by descending order of votes):

1. Participants are active learners
2. Peer to peer learning should form a key component of capacity building programmes
3. The trainer is rather a facilitation or a guide to learning
4. Participants discovering facts
5. The trainer is the sage on the stage (Fountain of knowledge)
6. Participants are passive learners

Question 5: How can the needs in the European market be matched with the talents in Africa?

Answers (by descending order of votes):

1. Facilitate networking and knowledge sharing based on clearly defined need and work toward mutually beneficial goals.
2. Generate and aggregate information on market need and opportunities that are relevant for stakeholders in both regions.

Question 6: What characteristics a platform should have to aid this matching?

Answers:

- Level of digital knowledge
- Simple, light, give equal chances to profiles
- Direct interactions with the grassroots
- Profile of start-ups and investors
- Profiling opportunities and opportunity creators, their value propositions and needs
- User friendly
- Interactive, simple to use, open creation

Question 7: What challenges do African and European start-ups face entering into markets on both continents?

Answers (by descending order of votes):

1. Infrastructures and skills gap
2. Lack of enabling policies
3. Lack of trust
4. Cultural Differences
5. Information gap

Question 8: How can a common digital market be created for African and European DIH and start-ups?

Answers (by descending order of votes):

1. Opportunities for African start-ups and businesses to pilot their solutions with the European context
2. Provide African ecosystem with open access to networks and partnerships with European digital ecosystem actors
3. Access to a larger market within Europe for African start-ups and businesses

Question 9: How can the opportunities be explored by Diaspora Communities and European Investors?

Answers:

- Through investor and start up matching activities.
- Through innovation showcases and presentations.
- Institutions have to create network with African diaspora groups and individuals in order to identify their interest groups and give them opportunities.
- By engaging start-up communities and also directly identifying and engaging start-ups
- Open calls for funding (cascade funding)
- Structured investment funds, to bring trust
- Having platforms for exchanges
- By given equal opportunity
- Diaspora can be active investors of African start-ups or match fund start-ups

Question 10: What tools and platforms provide access to the market in Africa? What features would you wish to see on such platforms?

Answers:

- Something modeled along the lines of the VC4A platform
- Africa need direct network with institutions
- Website and app portals. Features should include funding opportunities, etc
- Partnerships Building into the supply chain
- Matchmaking job features (w/ European organizations as well)
- Something that brings trust clean and fair offers
- Having platforms for exchanges
- By given equal opportunity
- Start-ups that are investment ready, VC4A, online platform that aggregates everything

Question 11: In order to promote business and investment opportunities in the African market, it will be important:

Answers (by descending order of votes):

1. To amplify the success stories of African fundraising efforts within Europe to build trust
2. To improve the expertise of African DIHs in raising funds be improved
3. To educate African politicians on digital innovations and market opportunities in Europe, namely through foreign missions and donor agencies

Foreseen outcomes

Question 12: Do the outcomes previously presented seem adequate to foster skills in Africa-Europe DIH partnerships?

Answers:

- They seem to be adequate for a start and should be evaluated during the process
- Yes
- Yes, quite holistic
- Yes, but more can be added

Question 13: Can you write down additional topics that can be added?

Answers:

- B2B matchmaking models Trade missions
- AI, Blockchain, IoT, Master class on Exporting and Transformation

Objectives

Question 14: Partnership-building programs should ultimately aim at better connecting them with DIHs both in Europe and in Africa. What should be the specific objectives of this programme?

Answers:

- Infrastructure and digital level
- knowledge differences
- Build sustainable collaboration channels
- Co-creation (business and innovations)
- Resource sharing, Fund sharing, joint project implementation

Structure & Tool

Question 15: Does the structure previously presented seem adequate to foster skills in Africa-Europe DIH partnerships?

Answers:

- Yes
- Yes, but not adequate

Question 16: Targeted interventions should include:

Answers (by descending order of votes):

1. Materials such as readings and case studies
2. Masterclasses
3. Webinars

Question 17: What should be the theme of the International Brokerage event?

Answers:

- Cross-continental Partnerships

Question 18: Who should be the invited speakers?

Answers:

- Yes
- Afrilabs member, Policy makers, OACPS head, I4policy

Question 19: Should it be interactive or expositive?

Answers:

- Yes

- Interactive

Methods

Question 20: What are the right methods to apply in the programme and its tools (bootcamps, events, etc)?

Answers (by descending order of votes):

9. Contact with experts
10. Case-based Exercises/ Case studies
11. Challenge-based learning
12. Lecture-showing/Telling
13. Video-Based Learning (VBL)
14. Discussion-Based Learning
15. Peer feedback
16. Hands-on work

Annex 2. Report containing the main outcomes of Deliverable D2.4

Challenges and Opportunities for Trans-Continental Collaboration

Introduction:

The insights present in this report were acquired through a series of four roundtables that were hosted covering three key themes: Improving access to funding for African DIHs and early-stage start-ups; Improving knowledge exchange between African and European DIHs; and Improving access to markets for African and European start-ups.

Approach:

The roundtables objectives were:

1. To undertake a detailed assessment of the needs, preferences, and challenges for cross continental and trans-continental collaboration
2. To identify recommendations from key stakeholders on the opportunities and interventions that could be leveraged to address the challenges identified.

The roundtables participants were:

1. Digital Innovation Hubs identified from the four Sub-Saharan African countries (Uganda, Ghana, Nigeria, and Tanzania) that participated in the state of play research
2. Digital Innovation Hubs from participating European partners
3. Start-ups from the African and European ecosystems
4. Investors

Roundtables' structure:

1. Sharing of insights from the state of play research
2. Lightning talks from invited representatives from key stakeholders
3. Break-out activities with participants around the key theme for each workshop
4. Debrief and closing

Needs, Opportunities and Recommendations Identified During the Roundtable Discussions:

1. Improving access to funding for African Digital Innovation Hubs and early-stage start-ups:
 - a. Needs:
 - i. To amplify linkages between start-up founders based on the African Continent with the African Diaspora Community in order to identify potential co-founders
 - ii. To know about investors/funds open to funding DIHs and start-ups in Africa
 - iii. DIHs need to link start-ups to potential mentors, business/corporate partnerships, training, and capital

- iv. To benchmark and contribute to policy formulation that might encourage an incentive-driven environment for funding
 - v. DIHs in Europe would like to spend time at African Digital innovation hubs and start-up companies to understand the context. This can be supplemented with exchange internships at European Universities and other entities for African DIHs
- b. Opportunities:
- i. Leverage key diaspora events happening within the European Union like the Uganda – UK diaspora event
 - ii. Invite or support African DIHs and start-ups to tap into European Industry events like the SLUSH event (<https://www.slush.org>)
 - iii. Invite European actors to participate in local industry events like the Tanzania Innovation Week (<https://hdif-tz.org/innovationweek>) to contribute to the dialogue based on their experience
- c. Interventions that address the needs identified and take advantage of the opportunities:
- i. “Seeing is believing”: AfriConEU should amplify the stories of successful investments and exits of African DIHs and start-ups on the European continent
 - ii. Regulatory guides
 - iii. Convening platform
 - iv. Work with Embassies
 - v. Business development service collaborations
 - vi. Investor education
2. Improving knowledge exchange between African and European DIHs to build their capacity:
- a. Needs:
- i. African DIHs need to build know-how on how to support due diligence for African start-ups that seek to enter or raise funding from the European market
 - ii. African DIHs would like to identify and grow a critical mass of European consultants and organizations that can offer quality business development services to African start-ups that seek to engage the European market
 - iii. African DIHs need linkages to funding geared towards supporting intermediaries or DIHs to provide technical assistance to start-ups looking to access European markets African DIHs would need to build market access know-how for start-ups looking to enter the European market

- iv. African DIHs would like to share data on their specific needs and the start-ups they support with European actors
 - v. European DIHs would like to access more open resources that can help them appreciate African ecosystems
- b. Opportunities:
- i. Networks like Afrilabs (<https://afrilabs.com/>) can be leveraged to build capacity at scale for African DIH
 - ii. African DIHs can be supported to tap into digital learning opportunities hosted by European hubs
 - iii. Research from various entities like OECD that provide insights on quality business development services can be tailored to the African context
 - iv. European DIHs are open to sharing success stories on what has worked for them
 - v. Networks like Google for Start-ups (<https://startup.google.com>) provide great learning and networking opportunities
 - vi. Enterprise Nation (<https://www.enterprisenation.com>) is a platform that has a critical mass of knowledge and consultants that can support the work of African DIHs
- c. Interventions that address the needs identified and take advantage of the opportunities:
- i. Embedded technical assistance
 - ii. Use a scorecard to build credibility
3. Improving access to markets for African and European start-ups:
- a. Needs:
- i. African DIHs need support on understanding market access compliance and certification requirements for start-ups to inform their support initiatives (for instance tax registration, digital information flow etc)
 - ii. There is a need to broker linkages with market access institutions like business associations for start-ups
 - iii. African DIHs need to understand cultural barriers and drive sustained cultural learning opportunities within the start-ups in their markets
 - iv. There is a need for African DIHs and start-ups to build competitive analysis capabilities on what European start-ups are undertaking
 - v. There is a need to collaborate with European DIHs and Governments to achieve the harmonisation of digital tax policies for start-ups
 - vi. A curation of market opportunities in Europe targeted towards Africa will be relevant

- vii. Collaborations with European foreign missions to educate African politicians on digital innovations and the market opportunities presented by European markets
 - viii. There is a lot of fragmentation and no apex body that can be relied on to drive or bring together African or European DIHs
 - ix. European DIHs and other supporting actors need to be supported to understand the African ecosystem
- b. Opportunities:
- i. Regional and continental African DIH associations provide opportunities for European start-ups to access market entry support
 - ii. Some initiatives have been supporting African start-ups to export their products/services to the European market. These include trade support organizations, development partner initiatives like International Trade Centre that can be leveraged for market entry
 - iii. There is a lot of un-utilized and affordable land that can be used by European start-ups for infrastructure set-up
 - iv. Leveraging predominantly European Start-up networks like Stripe Atlas (<https://stripe.com/atlas>), Google for Start-ups network and others to support African Start-ups and DIHs
 - v. Tapping into initiatives that subsidize the cost or lower non-tariff barriers to European market entry like trade associations, Stripe Atlas, Federation for Economic Development and Cooperation (BMZ - <https://www.bmz.de>)
- c. Interventions that address the needs identified and take advantage of the opportunities:
- i. Communities of practice: AfriConEU should establish communities of practice focused on market access for start-ups with European and African actor engagement
 - ii. Portal to address information asymmetry
 - iii. Market access needs assessment